

Tendencies of Loneliness and Well-being among General Population

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The present study aims at identifying the prevalence of loneliness, alleviation strategies to ward off it, along with wellbeing. The sample was selected using a purposive sampling technique. Around 240 individuals of different nationalities have been given an online survey form to fill. The researcher, using the discussion method with psychology students and elders, has prepared a checklist for collecting these experiences. Revised UCLA (R-UCLA) by Russell, Peplau, and Cutrona (1980) with 20 items with a reliability of 0.96 and Well-Being Scale (Singh, Junnarkar, & Kaur, 2016) with 28 items were utilized. Participants were asked to provide their ways of dealing with loneliness (termed lay strategies for the conceptual framework). Results showed that 23.75 % experiencing moderate degree of loneliness and 73.33 percent are experiencing a moderately high degree of loneliness. For loneliness, only the locality variable was found to be significant contributor ($r= 0.183^{**}$; $F=4.485$; $p=0.004$). For well-being, Age, Qualification and marital status were also significant. These details are disclosed in the relevant section. Qualitative analysis showed that in the sample, loneliness is expressed by the individuals who attribute it to their immediate family members and physical problems. It is noted that loneliness is alarmingly prevalent in today's society, thus identifying the reasons reported by the individuals as per their perceptions is imperative.

Keywords: Loneliness, well-being, lay strategies, self-perceptions, emotional immediate experiences

Loneliness is ubiquitous in today's world. WHO Director-General Dr. Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus quoted that loneliness 'grave global threat' (Desk, 2023). He cautioned that loneliness is the can lead to serious cognitive disorders and mental health concerns like depression and suicidal behaviour (WHO, 2023). In psychological research, loneliness is considered as the perception of an individual who, in dealing with certain stressful areas of his life, experiences lack of social support, and this would make one to be prone to severe mental health consequences (Kearns, Whitley, Tannahill, & Ellaway, 2015).

Loneliness, as per the APA dictionary of Psychology, is "affective and cognitive discomfort or uneasiness from being or perceiving oneself to be alone or otherwise solitary (American Psychological Association, 2015).

Definition of Wellbeing as per APA dictionary of Psychology- Wellbeing is "a state of happiness and contentment with low levels" of distress, overall good physical and mental health and outlook, or good quality of life (American Psychological Association, 2015).

In this article, the researcher assumed both parameters as polar extremes. The researcher is interested in using demographic variables such as gender, age, marital status, qualification, occupation, locality, residential status, and exploring the following questions.

- *R1:* Do the selected demographic variables affect loneliness?
- *R2:* Do the selected demographic variables affect Well-being?
- *R3:* How do emotional, attributional and behavioral components

associated with loneliness have any relation to predicting loneliness and well-being?

The researcher utilized qualitative analysis to answer R3.

Review of Literature

The investigator aimed to see the prominent relationship between the variables gender, age, marital status, family type, qualification, and locality on the experience of loneliness.

Gender

Expression of loneliness is more among women than men (Ernst, Klein, Beutel, & Brähler, 2021; Olawa et al., 2021; Barreto et al., 2020). Women could cater their services to others, albeit feeling lonely (Boehlen et al., 2023). The hard deal for women is social isolation (Guo, An, Luo, & Yu, 2021). Among Men, loneliness is found to be related to suicide ideation, while for women it leads to depression (Liu, Zhang, Yang, & Yu, 2020).

Age

Loneliness is identified as being among the younger in comparison to their seniors (Pop, Iorga, & Iurcov, 2022). But in the age group 30-74 years, as the age increases, loneliness seemed to decrease and increase after 74 (Pagan, 2020). Only the reporting of loneliness seemed to decrease with an increase in age (Barreto et al., 2020). Studies have shown that the peak age group for loneliness experience among males is of age group 47-55 years (Wang, Jiang, & Wu, 2023).

Family Type

In India, nuclear family and joint family systems are the most prominently discussed. Whereas in other countries, in place of the joint family concept, the extended family role is more emphasized. In a 1976 article, David Freeman echoed that we need extended family and shun away with the nuclear family system as much as possible (The Isolated Nuclear Family is Devastating, Says Family

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Therapist, 1976). This system, as observed in India, constitutes, living of all the family members, in-laws, in a single roof. As is observed in a chapter, couples relationship conflicts in the extended family system are though elicited are at the same time resolved by the other members of the extended family (Suzanne, Marlize, & Malan-Van, 2015). An empirical research article on the Indian Sample identified that females in Joint families procured significantly higher loneliness mean scores in comparison to males of both nuclear and joint families (Singh & Sirvastva, 2024).

Marital Status

A recent study showed that 'widowhood increases loneliness across age groups (Jiao, Zhang, Liu, & Xu, 2024). To have a partner to support financially had significant reductions in loneliness scores among married women in India (Shankar & Kidd, 2022).

Qualifications

Educational qualification often gives a sense of achievement, which, as per a study on seniors, is found to be associated with procurement of social support, thereby less reporting of loneliness. In the group with low educational qualifications, *higher scores of loneliness and emotional loneliness with social isolation* were observed (Gul, Chishti, & Bano, 2019).

Occupation

Being occupied with work in a professional work setting has many benefits. One of which is alleviation of loneliness. In one study, it is noted that empty-nest mothers (whose children are away from them) who are not occupied with any profession have more loneliness than empty-nest mothers with an occupation (Singh, Srivastava, & Maxton, 2023). Unemployment is definitely an unspoken predictor of loneliness and it is manifested prevalently among younger generation compared to elders (Shankar & Kidd, 2022).

Locality

In a large sample study across different locality sub-categories in Washington, it is identified that suburban individuals were less lonely in comparison to urban individuals. Prevalence rates are highest in large rural areas followed by urban, small rural and semi-urban areas (Abshire, Graves, Amiri, & Williams-Gilbert, 2020).

Coping Mechanisms

Research suggests that loneliness alleviation is possible with resorting to problem-focused coping methods (Deckx, van den Akker, Buntinx, & van Driel, 2018).

In a UK university students sample, the following strategies are applied for loneliness alleviation: "*Support-seeking, social isolation, self-reliance, problem-solving, and accommodation*". For accommodation, i.e., distraction, cognitive restructuring, acceptance and minimisation. Interestingly, the sample endorsed adopting strategies which help them to come out of it on their own rather than spending time with online activities such as Facebook, Instagram, etc. (Vasileiou et al., 2018).

Regarding children coping strategies, a study showed that the Lonelier the child feels, the more he becomes addicted to computer games. This was more prevalent in boys than girls (Kök Eren & Örsal, 2018).

Aims of the Study

- To study loneliness and its concomitants in the sample.
- To study lay strategies employed by the Sample in response to

loneliness.

- To observe patterns of loneliness and well-being in the sample.

Method

Participants

The sample is selected using a purposive sampling technique. 240 individuals (Gender-101 Male & 139 female; age range 16-20 yrs are 24; 21-30 yrs are 128; 31-40 yrs are 40; 41-50 yrs are 42; 51-60yrs are 5 and >70yrs is only 1 in the sample; Nationality- Indian 212, African- 13, Nepal-1, Tajik 1; Turkmenistan-4, Srilanka-2, Indonesia-1, Australian 1, USA -2, Palestine -2, and Mongolian 1 have been procured finally are by way of on-line survey forms.

Research Design

For the objectives mentioned, the researcher adopted a Mixed methods design, specifically, concurrent triangulation method.

Measures

Checklist prepared specifically through brainstorming (psychology students, normal people for their experiences during loneliness, counsellors etc..)

Revised UCLA (R-UCLA) by Russell, Peplau, and Cutrona (1980) with 20 items with a reliability of 0.96. Each item has 4 options 1= *Never*, 2= *Rarely*, 3= *Sometimes* and 4= *Often*. There is reverse scoring for some of the items. Reliability of the scale was 0.89 to 0.94

Well-Being Scale (Singh, Junnarkar & Kaur, 2016) with 28 items, which assesses Psychological Well-being, Positive perception about self and life, Goal Setting and Time Management and Positive Relationships is utilized. Each item has 5 options 1= *Very rarely true*, 2 =*Rarely True*, 3 = *Sometimes True*, 4 = *Often True* and 5 =*Always true*. α is in the range of 0.88 to 0.93 for the subscales.

Procedure

The research task started with the conceptualization of checklist preparation. The investigator raised a discussion to both senior and junior Master of Science students of Psychology, non-psychology people about four questions: emotional experiences post loneliness awareness, antecedents of loneliness, who they feel is the reason for their loneliness (precipitators), and activities they do to alleviate loneliness. Thus, 14 emotional experiences, 5 antecedents, 20 precipitators and 32 activities to alleviate loneliness were identified. These, along with demographical information, the tools enlisted above were composed into Google Form. These were distributed via invitation, sent to the counsellor, students, and international students at the University hostel to spread to their acquaintance. The form is open for 3 months from 1st week of January 2024 to the first week of March 2024. These were then validated and converted into SPSS format. Here, it is noted that subjects have given multiple opinions on the activities to alleviate their loneliness. Thus, the investigator had to code the themes and categorize them. Thus, these are grouped into 18 categories.

Statistical Analysis

Data was analyzed for descriptive statistics, t-test, ANOVA, regression analysis and Correspondence Analysis.

Results

Table 1*Levels of Loneliness and Well-being in the Sample*

Levels of Loneliness	Frequency	Percent	Levels of Well-being	Frequency	Percent
Low degree of Loneliness	3	1.3	Insignificant well-being	1	0.4
Moderate degree of Loneliness	57	23.8	low well-being	37	15.4
Moderate High degree of Loneliness	176	73.3	moderate well-being	104	43.3
High degree of Loneliness	4	1.7	high well-being	98	40.8
Total	240	100.0	Total	240	100.0

Table 2*Interpretative Statistics for Independent Variables w.r.t Loneliness Mean and Well-being Mean Scores*

		Loneliness Mean			r	t/F	Sig.	Well-being Mean		r	t/F	Sig.
		N	Mean	SD				Mean	SD			
Gender	Male	101	2.63	0.360	0.061	t= -0.942	0.347	3.72	0.605	0.080	t= -1.234	0.219
	Female	139	2.68	0.346				3.82	0.625			
Age	16-20	24	2.51	0.322	0.110	F= 2.925	0.089	3.48	0.532	0.206**	F=2.686	0.001
	21-30	128	2.65	0.373				3.73	0.610			
	31-40	40	2.72	0.279				3.92	0.505			
	41-50	42	2.75	0.305				3.89	0.720			
	51-60	5	2.41	0.555				4.24	0.547			
	61-70	No data	N/A	-								
	>70	1	2.45	-				4.07	-			
Occupation	Student	83	2.63	0.372	0.065	F= 1.000	0.318	3.70	0.602	0.048	F= 0.549	0.459
	Employee Govt	14	2.54	0.388				3.91	0.697			
	Employee Pvt Sector	72	2.69	0.319				3.76	0.649			
	Self-employed	36	2.69	0.348				3.98	0.542			
	Job Seeker (not yet employed)	8	2.64	0.341				3.63	0.526			
	Home maker	25	2.69	0.304				3.71	0.651			
	Retired	1	1.70	-				4.36	.			
Qualification	Athlete	1	3.35	-			3.61	.				
	SSC	10	2.66	0.539	0.020	F= 0.092	0.762	3.38	0.671	0.287**	F=4.972	0.000
	intermediate (+2)	14	2.54	0.308				3.32	0.424			
	Diploma	12	2.66	0.314				3.77	0.725			
	Graduation	104	2.67	0.377				3.70	0.627			
	Post- Graduation	92	2.68	0.300				3.96	0.536			
PhD	8	2.47	0.430	4.03				0.724				
Marital Status	Single	135	2.65	0.360	0.033	F= 0.261	0.610	3.68	0.622	0.151*	F=2.354	0.019
	Never Married	9	2.47	0.404				4.01	0.194			
	Married	92	2.70	0.332				3.91	0.619			
	Divorced	2	2.58	0.530				3.64	0.051			
Family Type	Widowed	2	2.38	0.106			3.48	0.833				
	Nuclear	169	2.68	0.344	-0.108	t= 1.681	0.094	3.82	0.610	-0.102	t= 1.584	0.114
Joint	71	2.60	0.367	3.68				0.629	F= 0.156			
Residential status	Independent house	105	2.63	0.364	0.109	F= 2.881	0.091	3.72	0.635	0.026		0.693
	Apartment (group house)	100	2.65	0.357				3.84	0.593			
	Hostel	23	2.74	0.201				3.84	0.539			
	Paying Guest	12	2.78	0.413				3.61	0.799			
Locality	Rural	34	2.47	0.359	0.183**	F=4.485	0.004	3.70	0.701	0.087	F= 1.813	0.179
	Semi-urban	27	2.73	0.236				3.71	0.720			
	Urban	113	2.66	0.329				3.77	0.568			
	Metropolitan	66	2.72	0.396				3.86	0.614			

Table 1 shows that in the sample 73.3 percent are in a moderately high degree of loneliness but half of the total sample also seems to have Moderate well-being

Table 2 shows that gender though not significant, based on mean scores, females experience high loneliness and at the same time express well-being. In occupation, athlete, though a single individual expressed both high loneliness and well-being mean scores. Both employees working in the private sector and self-employed had higher loneliness scores. But self-employed have higher well-being scores than employees of private sector and employees of government sector. Individuals belonging to a Nuclear family have reported both high loneliness and high well-being scores in comparison to a joint family. Paying guest have reported high loneliness mean scores, while those living in apartments and hostels have reported high well-being mean

scores. Individuals within 51-60 years age range had reported higher well-being mean scores, followed by 31-40 years in the sample. As per means 41-50 years age group has expressed higher loneliness. Qualification-wise, individuals with PhD qualifications reported high well-being mean scores, followed by individuals with post-graduation qualifications. Never married had higher well-being mean scores followed by married. Married people expressed higher loneliness mean scores. People living in Semi-urban and metropolitan areas had expressed higher loneliness mean scores, while metropolitan areas had also expressed higher well-being mean scores. These reasons are explored through qualitative analysis of some key elements like their experiences immediately after they feel loneliness, who they feel as perpetrators of their loneliness, when they feel lonely and coping strategies.

Table 3

Precursors of Loneliness Mean Scores and Well-being Mean Scores Comparison in the Sample

You feel Lonely when	Loneliness Mean	Well-being Mean	% of Total Sum
Never felt alone	2.42	4.86	1.20%
Others don't understand you	2.63	3.64	20.80%
You let down others' expectations of you	2.61	3.67	10.00%
Your actions, opinions are neglected by others	2.77	3.62	12.10%
When someone hurts your self-respect	2.65	3.85	33.80%
Others avoid you (isolate you)	2.69	3.78	10.40%
when it feels no one is there for me	2.70	4.37	1.70%
others	2.80	4.18	0.40%
enjoy solitude	2.58	4.62	1.20%
because of my own thinking pattern	2.47	3.54	1.20%
future concerns that seem heavy for my age	2.78	3.63	0.80%
I let down my self-expectations	2.85	3.63	1.20%
When I have free time	2.56	3.91	1.70%
Financial problems	2.45	3.14	0.80%
self-doubt, relationship problems	2.45	3.18	0.40%
introspect	2.90	4.19	1.20%
Things did not happened as expected	2.85	4.82	0.40%
When I don't spend time with God	2.85	3.89	0.40%

Table 3 showed that those individuals who reported to introspect scored a high loneliness mean score but the percentage is very less (1.20%). It shows that 'When high someone hurts your self-respect' response is majorly endorsed with a loneliness mean score of 2.65 followed by others don't understand. Similarly, for well-being scores highest mean score is identified for those who never felt alone (4.86), followed by 'things did not happen as they expected' (4.82).

Figure 2(a) shows the pattern of loneliness experience responses

and their impact on loneliness mean scores and well-being mean scores. Here, it indicates that a spike in well-being mean scores and slope in loneliness mean scores is noted for the items, never felt alone, enjoy solitude, introspection and things did not happen as expected. It could be interpreted subjectively that those who identified the problem nature inadvertently scored high mean scores on both loneliness and well-being mean scores [see Supplementary Material].

Table 4

Mean Scores of who makes you Feel Lonely Compared to Loneliness and Well-being Mean Scores

Who makes you feel lonely?	Loneliness Mean	Well-being Mean	% of Total Sum
Myself	2.68	3.79	21.70%
Husband	2.67	3.81	4.20%
Wife	2.93	3.39	2.50%
Father	3.00	3.48	0.80%

Mother	2.55	2.86	0.40%
Sister	1.00	4.89	0.40%
Mother-in-law	2.73	3.29	0.80%
Sister-in Law	2.08	4.04	0.80%
Relatives	2.48	3.66	2.90%
Friends	2.64	3.83	7.90%
Society	2.62	3.80	13.80%
Social Media posts	2.79	3.93	2.90%
Financial Problems	2.62	3.75	17.90%
Health Problems	2.51	3.8	3.30%
Work Companions	2.77	3.76	5.00%
People other than the individual (own family and friends)	2.83	3.21	0.80%
physiological and social problems	3.20	4.21	0.40%
work companions and financial problems	2.69	3.69	3.30%
work companions and financial and health problems	2.90	4.04	0.40%
Mother-in-law and financial problems	2.60	4.14	0.40%
Immediate family members, friends and relatives	2.66	4.08	1.70%
Family, relatives and financial problems	2.64	3.65	2.90%
Immediate family members	2.87	4.05	2.10%
Parents	2.55	4.36	0.40%
Immediate family members and health problems	3.05	2.93	0.40%
Family members and work companions	2.70	4.27	0.80%
Family members, relatives, financial and health Problems	2.63	3.66	0.80%

Table 5 shows that those who reported that they experience loneliness because of their immediate family members and health problems had higher loneliness mean scores (3.05) with lower well-being scores, but in the sample, the contribution is very less (0.40%). Those who reported that their sister is the one who makes them lonely scored less mean scores (1.00) on loneliness but higher well-being

scores (4.89) but their contribution is again very less in the sample (0.40%).

In addition to Table 5, Fig. 2(c) identified that those who reported 'mother-in-law' have scored higher loneliness mean scores, while lower well-being scores in the sample [see Supplementary Material].

Table 6

Activities to Alleviate Loneliness in Comparison to Loneliness Mean Scores and Well-being Mean Scores

Activities you prefer to deal with loneliness	Loneliness Mean	Well-being Mean	% of Total Sum
Never felt lonely	2.25	4.36	0.40%
Diversion to social media and human relationships	2.68	3.68	7.10%
Forget the problem (sleeping/wandering)	2.61	3.76	31.20%
feeling ecstasy through fantasy and supernatural elements (movies, animation, drama)	2.71	3.82	10.80%
Physical activities	3.08	4.38	1.70%
Cognitive activities - puzzles, creating articles, songs	2.64	4.03	1.70%
preoccupied with household work (cleaning, cooking)	2.56	4.03	3.30%
Social media and hobbies like drawing, shopping, etc.,	2.70	3.89	2.10%
Seeking pleasure from food, intimacy and entertainment	2.66	3.49	11.70%
looking at situation from new perspective	2.35	4.93	0.40%
Mindfulness like meditation, reading scriptures, praying to God	2.59	3.98	9.60%
withdrawn/ isolate oneself in a room	2.81	3.60	3.80%
Seek guidance/ support of other persons	2.61	3.86	6.70%
Spending time with Pets	2.78	3.65	7.10%
Playing videogames	2.97	4.29	1.20%
Go and sit at beach	2.50	3.32	0.40%
Seek attention of others by tantrums	2.47	3.14	0.80%

Supplementary Material 1

Correspondence Table

Activities you prefer to deal with isolation:	Locality				
	Rural	Semi-Urban	Urban	Metropolitan	Active Margin
Diversion to social media and human relationships	2.900	2.600	26.750	13.350	45.600
Forget the problem (sleeping/wandering)	31.750	16.150	97.550	50.350	195.800
feeling ecstasy through fantasy and supernatural elements (movie)	6.350	13.200	27.900	23.100	70.550
Physical activities	3.300	3.000	2.900	3.100	12.300
Cognitive activities - puzzles, creating articles, songs	.000	.000	7.900	2.650	10.550
preoccupying with household work (cleaning, cooking)	2.000	5.150	10.600	2.700	20.450
Social media and hobbies like drawing, shopping etc	.000	5.450	5.150	2.900	13.500
Seeking pleasure from food, intimacy and entertainment	7.800	8.150	37.100	21.300	74.350
looking at situation from new perspective	.000	.000	2.350	.000	2.350
Mindfulness like meditation, reading scriptures, and praying to GOD	12.350	.000	26.150	21.050	59.550
withdrawn/ isolate oneself in a room	.000	.000	16.400	8.850	25.250
Seek guidance/ support of other persons	9.450	8.150	11.050	13.050	41.700
Spending time with Pets	5.600	8.750	15.650	17.200	47.200
Playing videogames	.000	3.100	5.800	.000	8.900
Go and sit at beach	2.500	.000	.000	.000	2.500
Seek attention of others by tantrums	.000	.000	4.950	.000	4.950
Active Margin	84.000	73.700	298.200	179.600	635.500

Supplementary 2

Well-being Mean Scores to Marital Status

Marital Status	PsychW Mean		PP Self-Mean		GT Mean		PR Mean	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Single	3.80	0.666	3.59	0.741	3.66	0.650	3.63	0.740
Never Married	4.25	0.426	4.05	0.562	4.08	0.405	3.42	0.578
Married	4.00	0.614	3.85	0.713	3.88	0.686	3.85	0.744
Divorced	3.83	0.079	3.43	0.202	3.86	0.606	3.30	0.424
Widowed	3.61	0.550	3.43	1.010	3.43	0.808	3.40	1.131

Note. PsychW Mean = Psychological Wellbeing Mean scores; PPSelf Mean =Positive perception about self and life mean scores, GTMean=Goal Setting and Time Management mean scores and PRMean= Positive Relationships mean scores

Figure 2

Summary of Four Concomitants of Loneliness and Well-being in the Sample

Table 6 showed that highest loneliness mean scores were observed in those who reported that they do physical activities to address loneliness. Whereas the highest mean scores for well-being (4.93) are noted in those (0.40%) who reported looking at the situation from new perspective. But the next best mean scores of well-being are noted among the people who reported physical activities to address their loneliness.

In addition to the details given in Table 6, Fig.2(d) showed that those who use activities such as playing video games to address their loneliness experience both higher loneliness mean scores and well-being mean scores.

Discussion

The present study is more towards exploring the concomitants of loneliness from both quantitative and qualitative perspectives. In the sample studied, the investigator had identified that majority of the sample fit into loneliness categorization. Table 1 shows that 23.75% moderate degree of loneliness, 73.33 % moderately high degree of loneliness and an accumulated 1.67 percent of sample has in low degree and a high degree of loneliness. The quantitative inferential analysis provided answers to the research questions. Answer to R1 identified only a single variable locality. As per Table 1, semi-urban and metropolitan individuals of the sample had reported higher loneliness mean scores. In contrast to the study by Abshire, Graves, Amiri, and Williams-Gilbert (2020) the present study showed loneliness is prevalent in semi-urban areas in addition that metropolises. Metropolises have shown higher well-being mean scores in the sample (See Supplementary material 1) -dimension reduction techniques indicated that metropolises use coping ways such as forgetting problems by sleeping, shopping, etc., and also seek pleasure from food and intimacy. While semi-urban individuals adopted spending time with hobbies, feeling ecstasy with K-drama, anime, movies, etc. Regarding well-being, i.e., R2, quantitative inferential analysis derived three variables, namely age, qualification and marital status. Table 1 showed that 51-60 years old of the sample reported higher well-being scores. It is in congruence with the study by Wang, Jiang, and Wu (2023), where after 55, loneliness decreases. Although not significant, loneliness was most prevalent in the 41-50-year age group in the present study. Thus, this study is in congruence with it. Further, well-being is higher among the never married, while loneliness mean scores were higher in the married sample. This is in contrast to the study by Shankar and Kidd (2022), who identified that married individuals have a support system which who seemed to reduce loneliness among Indian women. The reason is evident in Table 5, which showed that those who reported that they feel lonely because of immediate family members and health problems scored high loneliness mean scores, while low well-being mean scores. Fig. 2(c) showed that this pattern was observed in those who reported the cause for their loneliness as mother-in-law.

Qualitative analysis for R3 indicated that in this sample, people felt lonely when they introspected. But this strategy was found to have considerably good well-being mean scores also. It is also noted that 33.80 % responded that they feel lonely when someone hurts their respect's item (See Table 3 & 2(a)). This procured the average loneliness mean score. Those who enjoy solitude had higher well-being mean scores in the sample. Table 4 and Table 6 indicate that those who resort to meditation, traveling, and immersion in the

experience of loneliness, as well as those who immerse themselves in playing video games, are the activated potential reactions to escalated loneliness. But playing video games seems to be elevating well-being scores in the sample (See 2(d)). The association of higher loneliness mean scores and playing video games is evident in the research work of Kök Eren and Örsal (2018). These identified that boys neglecting sleep continued to play the games and became computer game addicts in the face of loneliness. It could be that, as cited by Nebel and Ninaus (2022) playing these games could help them improve their mood states forgetting the source of the discomfort.

This study focused on several qualitative aspects to gain knowledge on the immediate experiences of loneliness in general among individuals. But loneliness was prevalent in those who wanted to forget the issue and move forward. Never married showed higher well-being scores, while married higher loneliness scores. Never married showed higher Psychological Well-being Mean scores; Positive Perception about Self and life Mean scores, Goal Setting and Time Management Mean scores, except Positive Relations Mean Score, which are higher for married in the sample (See Supplementary Material 2). The sample with loneliness seemed to attribute their loneliness to immediate family members. Only meditation seems to be associated with both lessening loneliness and increased well-being. But playing videogames seemed to be associated with both high loneliness and well-being mean scores.

Limitations of the Study

The present study is an online survey with a limited sample. Further, there is no data available for 61-70 years age group. Thus, the study only projects an analysis of the data anonymously obtained but not standard generalizable results. An attempt to see the visualized pattern is made but more in-depth data points need to be identified with more data being collected.

Conclusion

Loneliness has become very prevalent. More than 70 % in a small sample indicated this. So it is imperative to conduct several action research studies on this issue while considering the lay strategies employed by the lonely.

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